

Re-Thinking the Value of Corporate Learning Systems in the South African Context: A Literature Review

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Abstract. Learning platforms offered by corporate organisations to their employees are often evaluated using learning evaluation frameworks. The business value of Information Systems literature remains sparse in this evaluation. From a sustainability perspective, this research asks if value could be considered beyond the narrow self-interest of the organisation. We aim to explain dimensions that can inform corporate learning system value creation in the context of a developing economy such as South Africa by reviewing the IS, value, and learning literature critically, and sensitive to the socio-economic conditions of this setting, suggesting how CLS value can be reconceptualised. This research is limited by its literature orientation, inviting expansion through empirical application of its findings.

Keywords: Value, Sustainability, Corporate Learning Systems.

1 Introduction

The 2002 United Nations (UN) Johannesburg World Summit on Sustainable Development made two commitments still pressing today, broader participation and a longer-term view (#26), and the private sector duty to “contribute to the evolution of equitable and sustainable communities and societies” (#27) [1]. South Africa (SA) since led their institutionalisation by including social and environmental factors into codes of corporate governance [2]. The value concept also expanded in this time, shifting from seeing capital (as a store of value) as purely financial, to include dimensions such as social and relational, intellectual, and human capital [3]. These commitments were consolidated into the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [4], and included in the SA governance codes stating that “the licensor of the organisation is not just those individuals and entities within its narrowly defined value chain, but society as a whole” [5]. In the SA integrated reporting context, skills development is a high quality material example [6].

Private sector corporate organisations often avail a variety of learning technologies, which we call Corporate Learning Systems (CLS), to their employees to develop their skill. Skill being both a credentialling unit and a management tool [7]. Despite this interest, the value of CLSs is often articulated in terms of benefit to the organisation itself, using frameworks such as the Kirkpatrick model [8] and the recently published ISO standard for learning measurement, ISO/TS 30437:2023 [9].

Within this context, we aim to answer the question: *Which dimensions inform CLS value creation in a developing economy such as South Africa in a way that serves a*

more representative set of interests. We do so through a systematic literature review at the intersection of the value, technology, and the developing economy context, and offer suggestions about how prevailing value perspectives might shift to extend the benefit of learning efforts in corporate organisations towards better societal outcomes.

This paper is structured as follows. Section 2 offers a contextual background that considers the concept of value, and the technology underpinning CLSs. Section 3 outlines the research method. Section 4 presents the literature against contextual themes. The implications of the results are discussed in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 concludes this paper by outlining limitations and suggesting further research.

2 Context and Background

We start by defining value as usefulness from the subjective perspective of a recipient [10], this subjectivity bound by recipient context. We consider value in terms of three contextual dimensions: the socio-economic context of SA, technological innovations in CLS, and an expanded conceptualisation of value. We ask what opportunities for value realisation may occur at their confluence.

In the first dimension we note that the political liberation in 1994 has not yet translated in meaningful reduction of economic inequality. Despite several initiatives, such as progressive policies on the role of organisation in society, and re-thinking of how skill should be developed [11], implementation is often done superficially [12]. Skill, a desired goal of learning, may be a mechanism by which life outcomes of individuals can be improved. In the modern world, it changed from being developed by early adulthood and practiced in the working career, to a continuity of learning new, updating existing, and discarding obsolete skills [7]. This requires a reorientation to life-long learning, resurfacing agency in the choice of skill developed.

The second dimension involves CLS innovations and includes process and people in addition to technology, serving individual and organisational learning [13]. Artificial Intelligence (AI), for example, facilitates dynamic learning experiences, going beyond the original task of digitising courses and tracking activity.

The third dimension tracks the evolution of value. We are interested in the continuation of the shift in the “for whom” of value generation that originated in the 1990s. It manifests in two channels that fall under sustainability. The first, framed around the UN SDGs, and the second about emerging environmental, social and governance (ESG) concerns and the development of more inclusive value reporting such as “six capitals” [2]. The second and third dimensions have been a subject of combined interest in IS, such as “twin transformations” that aligns digital and sustainability transformation [14].

3 Research Method

We approach this study from the critical paradigm which requires us to state our perspective upfront, an interest in the role of IS to “lead to an emancipation”, “a state of justice, freedom and material well-being for all” [15]. Our interest is equally in the

vibrancy and health of the human employee working in a corporate entity, the corporate entity itself in a competitive marketplace, the societal construct that encompasses both.

The literature review favours problematisation over gap-spotting and looks broadly, seeking perspectives beyond the core corpus of a field, and narrowly, by critically zeroing into a limited set of articles. We combine several dimensions around the core theme of value. We problematise existing knowledge on the broad phenomenon of value, applied to CLSs, in the context of a developing economy. Our approach follows Templier and Paré [16]’s analysis of Schryen [17]. It is guided by a systematic and transparent procedure [16], and takes a broad perspective. Being rooted in IS though, we used the Litbaskets tool to perform IS-targeted Scopus searches [18], complemented by wider Scopus and Web of Science searches, following the IS tradition of engagement with reference disciplines [19]. These searches were conducted in May 2025.

Using the Litbaskets categorisation we included most journals in the “2XS” to “M” baskets and selected journals up to the “3XL” basket. No journal restrictions were placed on the Web of Science query. In both cases, Title, Abstract, and Keyword fields were searched using a time span from 2015 to 2025. The narrower focus of Litbaskets yielded 1,332 results that were evaluated on title and keyword. Articles narrowly focused outside our interest were excluded. This resulted in 294 papers.

The Web of Science query resulted in 8,293 articles, requiring refinement. In the first round we extracted a unique set of journal categories from the result set and tagged them for relevance. For example, the category of ‘Agronomy’ was tagged as low relevance, while ‘Information Systems’ was highly relevant. The next refinement was based on journal title. For example, the journal *Corporate Communications* would be tagged as low relevance, and *Journal of Education and Work* would be tagged as high relevance. This resulted in 2,051 articles. Titles and keywords of these were then used to tag for inclusion or exclusion. Reasons for exclusion included redacted articles, primary/secondary education focus, a methodology focus, or articles otherwise too narrowly focused outside our interest. We included articles with an education focus related to the world of work. This left us with 306 articles.

The third iteration analysed the union of the two sets by reading abstracts and recording each article in Microsoft Excel, indicating how many of our three dimensions it covered, then giving a score between 1 and 4 based on relevance. A score between 1 and 7 was calculated, adding the number of dimensions to the relevance score. Articles with high relevance that covered most dimensions, scoring 6+ were promoted. From the rest we added only those particularly relevant to a specific research dimension. So 118 articles were tagged for sourcing, of which 113 were ultimately sourced. From a forward/backward search 9 more were added, resulting in a total of 122 articles. In the fourth round, articles were loaded into the NVivo qualitative analysis program for an orientational reading of their introductions and conclusions. In this reading, initial thematic coding was conducted. We also identified setting and location cases.

We evaluated our result set from three perspectives. Firstly, we considered the research tradition. The articles comprised 75% of the various “baskets” of IS, 12% from Education and Educational Research, 6% from Business and Economics, and the remaining 7% from Development Studies, Science and Technology, Social Sciences, and Sociology. Secondly, we considered the locations where research was conducted. In

46% of the articles, no clear location was specified, 38% specified the global South, and 15% the global North. Finally, we considered the organisational setting, with 26% not being clear, 50% in corporate or business settings, 14% in educational settings, and the remaining 10% in hybrid and public sector organisations or in social settings.

The result represents the IS research tradition with some input from business, development, and education. It includes representation from the global South, is mainly based in corporate settings. Open coding of the combined set was done based on our three themes. In an orientational reading of the 122 selected articles and a deep read of 45 of specific relevance, inductive coding was used to gain an overview of relevant concepts related to each theme. On the theme of CLS, 46 codes were identified representing 91 articles, on value, 47 codes representing 83 articles, and on developing economies, 10 codes representing 21 articles. Codes were consolidated and grouped into sub-codes, plotted and analysed in the Freeform tool until we had a coherent picture of the phenomenon of interest. Next follows a thematic synthesis of key findings.

4 Results

From the literature, we now elaborate observed themes along the dimensions of CLSs, value articulation, and the developing economy context. The first and last having specific importance from the contextual and subjective value perspective [10].

4.1 Corporate Learning Systems

We start by considering the contextual factors influencing the deployment of learning systems in our chosen setting of commercial organisations. We consider systems broadly, to encompass people, process, and technology [17]. So too, is technology seen broadly to include what supports “e-learning-enhanced organizational learning” [13].

The Organisational Context. *Knowledge economy.* Emphasis is placed on skill and the dynamics of skill supply and demand [8]. Employees are valued in terms of the knowledge and skill they hold [20]. While organisations may provide CLS infrastructure, the responsibility for investing energy into their skill and “value” often rests on employees, for whom the value may mean employability and livelihood.

Skill as unit of interest. Skill is key to developing organisational capability, work- and learning practices [21, 22]. Granularity of skill supports creation of “stackable” skill assemblages specific to very particular needs [23]. Such assemblages could combine few deep proficiencies with more shallow proficiencies in a π -shaped skill profile [24]. Skill is deployed alongside AI more often, working with AI itself a key skill [25].

Skill formation and assembly. Tertiary education no longer suffices to ensure ongoing employability [26]. Reconfiguring education systems to be responsive to workplace needs takes time [27]. Micro-credentialling allows differentiation between qualification and industry need to supplement qualification with emergent skills [23, 26].

Workplace learning. Pedagogical approaches for adult learning to include modalities that support learner participation, self-directedness, agency, practical application, and problem-centeredness [28, 29].

Capability development. Learning in organisations is linked to organisational learning, by which value is created through differentiating capabilities and efficient work practices [22]. Individual learning activity may contribute to the development of capabilities aligned with objectives, delivered efficiently through e.g. e-learning [13]. It continuously produces, imparts, shares, and leverages knowledge [30, 31] that produces intangible value in intellectual and human capital [8].

Learning culture. Developed when organisations systematically develop continuous learning. Its existence cannot negate that power relations exist that may determine the learning agenda. Top-down, the socially constructed nature of skill influences which are valued and what work is considered “skilled” [32]. Bottom-up, knowledge contributors and observers multiply and access becomes more widely available [33].

The Technology Context. *Learning analytics.* Serving the original IS goal of managing inventories [19], now including learning and skill, with some unrealised potential [13]. Visibility may take on a valence of surveillance, with considerations such as privacy, boundaries, and ownership of data to be considered in value exploration [33, 34].

Credentiailling. “Talent clouds” projected to enable new work arrangements informed by credentiailling of micro-learning and skill [34]. Expressed through points, leaderboards, and badges to drive engagement and continuity, allowing employees to signal employability in- and outside the current workplace [23, 26].

AI in the ecosystem. Enables new ways of learning such as knowledge-based learning environments [35]. Can redefine structure of work [36], and when developed into a capability, support organizational learning [37] in a reconfigured learning-knowledge-skill-work nexus.

Social learning. Enables communities of practice, information exchange, self-regulation, and self-efficacy [28]. Value potential of knowledge work supported by peer-to-peer learning increases [24]. Can contribute to open participation in knowledge and power structures [38].

Learning platforms. CLS often has a platform nature, generating data that becomes a distinct and differentiating source of value [34, 39], reducing transactional friction in a demand/consumption model such as massive open online courses (MOOCs) [34, 40], and being extensible with content, services, or apps [39]. Open platforms allows greater parity in knowledge flows,[40] but can also monopolise value away from the periphery of e.g. developing economies [39].

4.2 Value

We approach the concept of value with an expanded view that departs from the common commercial aim of generating returns on financial capital, to include human, intellectual, social and relational, natural, and manufactured capital. Capital is defined as a store of value that can be leveraged to achieve the organisation’s desired outcomes [3].

IS Business Value (ISBV). Profitability. Tangible value of IT investment often frames it around cost or time savings, or enabling new revenue channels [41]. Learning, too, can be a contributor to competitive profitability [42]. Causality though is difficult to determine [43] and may require a disaggregated study of how different types of IT contribute to value creation [17].

Efficiency. Core to ISBV creation [44], desired efficiencies do not always realise or take time to do so. The “productivity paradox” shows that IT value realisation requires more than technology and should include consulting, services and training [45]. While technology proficiency can positively influence employee productivity, e.g. working with AI, some tasks better support positive productivity outcomes than others [25]. Skill attainment can be more efficiently achieved aided by technology [46], especially for relatively static knowledge types [47]. Contextualised initiatives such as corporate universities can improve efficiency of learning and knowledge absorption [48].

Intangible value. Much added market value from IT spending cannot be accounted for on balance sheets. “Intangibles” such as IT-related capabilities, human resource practices, and how IT is used could also be priced into market value [45] and should be part of a complete ISBV picture [43]. Such value can be realised through processes, combining IS capabilities and assets to generate internal value [17]. Capabilities, with resources, shape the resource-based view (RBV) of the firm. When valuable, rare, difficult to imitate, and constructed to make it difficult to achieve similar outcomes via substitutes, capabilities become core, supporting sustainable competitive advantage [22]. Routinised IT-supported work practices is a form of organisational learning that can produce new capabilities [22], of which learning is an example [42].

Capability development. Technology resources and processes can become so embedded in a capability that trying to disaggregate the value of the parts may become impractical [43]. Organisations may use e-learning as key to the knowledge and experience processes required to build capabilities [47]. When capabilities are reconfigurable in response to environmental changes, they are considered dynamic [21, 47]. Capability can also mean the “substantive freedom to choose a life that one has reason to value” Amartya Sen’s definition [49]. In turbulent times, organisations may simultaneously need organisational learning capabilities while supporting individual capability development, as long as it serves long term interests such as career development [49].

Innovation. Opportunities for innovation are created when IT combines with human skill [21, 24] or where it facilitates the creation or sharing of knowledge [46]. Technology-enabled learning can support organisational learning, which together with a learning culture can support innovation [30]. Knowledge, central to learning, becomes valuable when shared, collaborated around, reducing risk, and supporting innovation [30].

Adoption and use. Core to success models [41] and ISBV [43], adoption and use of IT can also elevate market valuation [44, 45]. IS adoption must be aligned with strategy [43]. From a learning perspective, initiatives require alignment of organisational goals to individual needs and the learning capabilities employed to achieve specified goals [13]. Surprisingly, alignment is still somewhat underexplored [13, 21].

Value Generated for Individuals. CLSs may offer value to individuals by developing their capabilities in Sen’s sense, noted earlier. This could be done by developing skill

that broaden life choices. Realised choices, or functionings, are effected through conversion factors that transform potential into actual [50], of which CLS may be one. We should then view skill not just as an organisational commodity, but also in its value to the individual by increasing prospect optionality [51]. Fairness in access brings a social justice dimension into this conversion process [52], especially in the socio-historical context of a society with high inequality such as SA. Individual meaning may change through employed life, along with goals, aspirations and career trajectory. Different interventions may be differently valued over time [52]. Extrinsic factors such as earning ability may impact skill valuation over intrinsic factors such as enjoyment and meaning [53]. While technology could enable skill, skills that support technology proficiency promote confidence and self-efficacy [53], which can support life-long learning [28]. The dynamism of knowledge economies elevates the value of skill and life-long learning as the half-life of skill prioritises extrinsic factors of employability and promotability [29]. Engaging digital learning environments that facilitate continuous learning can support greater individual commitment to the working environment, benefitting individual and organisation [31]. Making learning attainment easier, e.g. through micro-credentials, allows modularity that further supports life-long learning habits [23].

Value Generated for Society. Licensed by society, organisations' sustainability in their constituencies is an important value consideration [5]. When values imbued in technology, e.g. AI, run counter to those of the societies they serve, such as equality, harmony, and self-determination [54], the social sustainability of implementing organisations may be eroded, risking reputation and financial sustainability [36]. The rarity of hybrid organisations that serve dual financial and social purposes [49] may prompt organisations to build mutually reinforcing "twin transformation" capabilities, combining digital and sustainability initiatives [14] instead. Integrated reporting makes it explicit for whom value is generated [2], e.g. managers, employees, and citizens. Human capital can add value beyond organisational self-interest to include individuals in the socio-economic conditions of their communities [8]. It may be problematic when seen in terms of productivity and employability only, potentially neglecting aspects of work that are rewarding for the worker [32]. It may de-value those who did not have the opportunity to invest in their own skill. Instead, skill may need to be seen as a public good [20]. This is important in SA where the historically disadvantaged still lag behind their advantaged counterparts, despite having similar skill or human capital levels [50].

4.3 The Developing Economy Context of SA

Developing economies were well represented in the selected articles, and many sources used in the prior two dimensions stem from the developing world. Further to the Context and Background, we highlight a few additional themes observed in the literature.

Conditions. The digital divide challenges sustainability in the modern world in terms of access to technology and the digital skills required to earn a livelihood [54, 55]. In the developing world the divide may be wider, potentially exacerbating inequality as

those with digital skills are better positioned to increase their options in competitive labour markets [40]. Countering it is digital inclusion, with benefits beyond financial, e.g. social engagement, autonomy, identity and participation [53]. Technological restrictions in knowledge access can have implications for power relationships, although organic modes of interaction can upset linear knowledge-power perspectives [33].

Social justice, in the sense of not having to bear more burdens than what one ought to bear [56], is an important socio-historic consideration in SA, and needs consideration when the responsibility for life-long learning is placed disproportionately on the individual [34]. Platforms may offer more freedom, but also work counter to social justice aims, such as gig work's potential to increase worker precarity [34, 52].

Responses. Developing transferable skill such as IT may have multiplier effects beyond the workplace, adding to the total skill in the job market, and better local economy outcomes [55]. For this to realise, skill development must take a career-oriented view [49]. Without considering political and economic conditions, skill development may not lead to decent and dignified work [32]. Considering outcomes, aspects beyond the econometric should be considered to include Sen's capabilities and functionings [50].

While policies such as National Qualification Frameworks were developed to make education more work-relevant [27], increased rates of skill obsolescence may require a nimbler approach, such as formalising stackable skills [55]. Broad-strokes policies can miss the variety of circumstances that individuals find themselves in, becoming counterproductive by enforcing standard trajectories and limiting benefit pathways [52].

5 Discussion

Following a critical approach to the literature review, we problematised the broad phenomenon of value as it relates to CLSs, in a developing economy context and gained a more nuanced understanding of the current knowledge. Let us consider some implications. CLSs are deployed in competitive corporate settings that prioritises productivity, efficiency, and effectiveness. Competitive advantage is sought by developing unique and differentiating capabilities through innovation and organisational learning, which in turn depend on timely and appropriate skill deployment. Existing learning frameworks do not adequately cater for this need for agility in developing and deploying skill. A utilitarian view of skill puts the employee at the mercy of skill obsolescence, which risks neglecting career prospects and work well-being over time. When responsibility for developing skill rests mostly on the employee, especially when their value becomes measured purely in terms of skill, it risks a problematic redefinition of the employee-employer relationship that may result in increased worker precarity that a developing economy with high levels of unemployment can ill afford.

The CLS technology artefact is sometimes only vaguely described. Since technology-enabled learning modalities need to fit the environment and purpose for which they are deployed, there is room to better describe the task-technology fit as it relates to CLS capability. The overlap of KM and learning disciplines mediated by AI appears to be inadequately explored in this context. From a CLS platform perspective, platform value

could be better described, such as how self-directedness and agency could benefit employees, potentially balancing out benefit biased to platform owners and managers.

From a value perspective, the extended view is well established, as is the concept of intangible value. What remains challenging is describing how value gets generated. Skill may be a potential lens. How CLSs can close education-workplace gaps may be another. Value to the individual is perhaps the least well described in the organisational literature, while it is a focus area in ICT4D. While there is a clear link between learning, skill, employability, and livelihood, seeing it purely from a supply-and-demand perspective may weigh the organisational benefit disproportionately high in relation to the individual benefit in the SA socio-economical and socio-historical realities. Given the role of organisations in bridging education-workplace gaps, we may take a perspective of longer-term benefit to not just the livelihood-earning value of the employee but also supporting longer-term life aspirations. The maturing perspective of sustainability has broadened the description of value generated by organisations to include individual and societal stakeholders. So have the expanded views of capital, bearing in mind the problematic side of the human capital perspective. What may be lacking are more precise descriptions of the societal conditions that may benefit from CLS-mediated outcomes.

6 Conclusion, Limitations, and Future Research

Considering the ways in which the extant literature articulates IS and CLS value in the context a developing economy such as SA, we made the case for a legitimate broadening of stakeholder interest and a more comprehensive perspective of value that corporate entities can help realise. This requires description beyond the ‘what’ of value, to the ‘how’ or mechanisms by which value is generated. Despite the relative abundance of value literature in terms of ISBV, there is a comparative scarcity when the filters of CLS and the developing economy context are applied. We described the ingredients for novel approaches to the conceptualisation of value, to be used in more contextual and descriptive articulations.

The perspective of this research is limited by its geographical and socio-historical bias to SA, and research from other developing economies would benefit the overall view on value. Further research could augment this literature review with empirical enquiry into the value perspectives of employees and organisations.

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